

Historical conditions and climatic events from the 18th century BC to the 13th century BC.

- **Moses:** extra-biblical, probably 13th century BC.
- **Akhenaten:** birth name Amenophis IV; Reign about 1351 to 1334 BC.
- Amenophis III: government around 1388 to 1350 BC, construction of the temple of Karnak, Pest in Egypt, tries to break the power of the priests of Amun with the cult of the sun, has female statues of gods erected, veneration of the goddess Maat, daughter of the sun god, who was responsible for order and harmony.
- Amenophis II (Amenhotep): government about 1428 to 1397
- **Moses:** Exodus from Egypt 1442 BC, date according to the Bible
- Thutmosis III: government around 1486 to 1425 BC and Hatshepsut; Expansion of Egypt to the Near East, Syria (Mitanni came from northern Syria) and acquisition of trading partners and tributes
- Ahmose I: government around 1560 to 1525 BC; worship the moon god. Severe weather pillars and expulsion of the Hyksos from sub-Egypt; Restoration of power in Nubia and Canaan. Ahmose I lays the foundation stone for the New Kingdom. (the 18th dynasty)
- Pharaoh Kamose set around 1540 BC, continued the struggle against the Hyksos, which had subjugated parts of Egypt.
- As a result of the eruption of the Thera volcano, chaotic conditions are likely to arise in the Middle East, which will lead the Hebrews to flee to Egypt. The Hyksos (shepherds and traders) invade the eastern Nile Delta from Syria and Palestine. They build the 15th dynasty there (foreign rule of the Hyksos), followed by the 16th dynasty of local kings,
- **Between 1600 and 1627 BC Volcano Thera** erupts in the Aegean Sea in the 3rd century BC. It was the strongest volcanic eruption in the past 10,000 years. It destroys the highly developed Minoan culture with the centre of Knossos in Crete and its commercial branches on the coasts of the eastern Mediterranean. The mega-tsunami that followed the outbreak destroyed ships and port facilities from the Libyan coast via the Nile Delta, Palestine and Lebanon to Sicily. The foundations of the Minoans' trading empire disappear into the sea. The ashes thrown into the stratosphere and the gases must have caused a hemispherical winter for years. There were also famines¹ during the 13th Dynasty Intermediate approx. in 1760 or after 1640 BC.

¹ See also summary program on Phoenix from May 28, 2019 Riddles of History – The Search for Atlantis.